

Reproducing the paper "Measuring Influence on Instagram: A Network-Oblivious Approach"

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ABSTRACT

This report details the steps taken to reproduce the paper "Measuring Influence on Instagram: A Network-Oblivious Approach" as part of Exercise 2, from the lecture course Experiment Design in Data Science, WS2021. The goal is to check whether the information given in the paper is sufficient to reproduce the results reported; to review if there are statistically significant differences between the reported and reproduced results; and finally whether the values reported in the paper could stem from the distribution sampled by the reproduced experiments.

Overall, it was found that the graphs from the original paper can be easily recreated using the data source provided by the authors. However, this is where the 'easy' reproduction cases as the authors did not report details such as code, environment, parameter information for clustering or regressors used, making the reproduction of the remainder of the paper an extremely cumbersome task. Our reproduction therefore lead to similar results in some cases, but also differed significantly in others.

CCS CONCEPTS

• **Information systems** → **Social recommendation**; *Social advertising*.

KEYWORDS

Social Media, Instagram, Influence, Ranking, Influencers, Reproducibility, Regression, Significance Testing

1 PAPER SUMMARY

The paper by Segev et. al. aims to find a model that is independent of a network for scoring and ranking influential users of Instagram, a popular visual content sharing online social network (OSN). At the time of writing the paper, Instagram was the second largest OSN in the world where users share photos and videos. Certain posts shared by 'more influential' users are viewed by more users than those shared by less influential counterparts. This is the basis of the question behind the paper relevant for brand building and audience targeting via influencer marketing: How to identify influential Instagram users?

The authors claim that a 'graph-based approach used in other OSNs is a poor fit for Instagram', for which they suggest several modeling approaches instead. They state that they will base their model on user statistics and regression to measure users' influence, and as a starting point, provide a link from where to download the data ¹.

¹Zipped data source, https://klear.com/sigir/instagram_data.zip

According to the details provided in the paper, their approach follows these steps:

- Review current user ranking strategies for OSNs.
- Postulate how to measure influence: ("We say the influence of an Instagram user (Instagrammer) is the expected exposure their content would receive, or, their expected number of views per post.")
- Load the datasets.
- Measure basic statistics and produce three graphs. Specifically: (a) (log) Average Views per Instagrammer; (b) Views per Followers; (c) Views per Likes.
- Perform univariate outliers removal.
- Transform likes and followers statistics using a log scale: $f(x) = x/\ln(x)$.
- Expand the previous dataset to include several additional features: likes, comments, followers, square root of (likes x followers), followers/post, comments/likes and focus.
- Build regression models using the expanded dataset. First, two baseline models for measuring influence by using the user's audience size (followers) or engagement level (number of likes) with the help of a Linear Regression model. Then also build models using Ridge Regression and Random Forest.
- "Meta-algorithm expansion": separate data into subsets by K-Means clustering and then build a multiple-regression model for each subset. This is a strategy to cope with the "vast differences between celebrity statistics and those of micro-influencers".
- Perform recursive feature elimination to generate a subset of informative features.
- Evaluate the models by "comparing the order of the predicted influence with the real influence allows us to rank users" using two performance measures: R^2 and r_s (Spearman's rank correlation coefficient).
- Use five-fold cross validation technique to avoid the problems of a model tuned specifically to the test data. Average the results on the five test cases.

2 STRATEGY / REPRODUCTION STEPS

The authors do not provide any code and the paper does not give any information on the used programming language, environment, libraries etc. In our reproduction process we set up a notebook with python environment and made the code publicly available ².

²Reproducing the paper "Measuring Influence on Instagram, a Network-Oblivious Approach, <https://github.com/Frodl/Reproducing--Measuring-Influence-on-Instagram-A-Network-Oblivious-Approach-.git>

The notebook was set up to load the data and gain a deeper understanding of the logic of the paper and the approach taken by the authors, as well as to verify the sequence of steps outlined above. The data was downloaded from the given source and the three graphs from the paper were easy to reproduce after minimal preprocessing.

Next, we identified subsequent steps the authors took in order to reproduce the results from the paper. In doing so, it was clear that certain details were missing early on. For instance, no information was given on the environment or libraries used, but the graph colour codes and structure hinted towards Python's default Matplotlib's ³ pyplot graphing settings ⁴. Thus, we decided to use this environment along with the scikit-learn library ⁵ for reproducing the models in later steps. The paper again did not state which package/library was used for building the regression models.

Figure 1: Reproduction steps. Note that the outlier removal was not possible to reproduce.

Finally, our results were compared to those from the paper. The comparison revealed that reproduced results using R^2 were not as good as those using the r_s - Spearman's rank correlation coefficient.

3 DIFFICULTIES AND KEY FINDINGS

As briefly mentioned before, the main cause for our reproduction struggles was the missing source code. The author's state that "out-of-the-box" models for both types of regressors were used, but since the code environment is not provided, nor any library to which to refer to, it is not clear what they mean by "out-of-the-box".

Secondly, we found that the dataset size slightly differs from the size of the downloadable data set. The authors did not address this discrepancy in their paper, but it could be one of the sources of the differences in our reproduced results.

Furthermore, the authors state that there was an outlier removal step, specifically: "To avoid these sorts of odd behaviors, we performed univariate outliers removal, ignoring the top and bottom posts for users with posts statistics above 2 standard deviations".

It was not clear from this section of the paper when exactly the outlier removal took place. If the outlier removal was done on the given dataset before the plotting of the graphs, the graphs would look different than the ones that were reproduced without outlier removal. Had the authors removed everything above and below 2σ in the given dataset already, the size of the dataset would have decreased by about 5% (assuming a perfect Gaussian distribution, 95% of the data lies between 2σ of the mean) compared to the numbers stated in the paper. Referring to the paper the dataset

³Matplotlib's default graphing settings, https://matplotlib.org/stable/users/prev_what's_new/dflt_style_changes.html

⁴Matplotlib's pyplot, https://matplotlib.org/stable/api/_as_gen/matplotlib.pyplot.html

⁵Scikit-learn, <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/>

contains a total of 940439 posts by 115044 Instagrammers. Our analysis of the raw data showed a total of 1422894 posts by 114781 Instagrammers. This is again not the case (940439/1422894 is not 5% less). However, even if it was clear when this removal took place, a reproduction would not be feasible. Without further information on the handling of the dataset it is not possible for us to combine the different csv files and trace which posts exactly should be removed. As a consequence, an outlier removal step could not be reproduced as part of this report.

Key findings and assumptions about the experimental design:

- No details were given on the coding environment, libraries used, hardware or software background. Therefore, we ran our notebooks using python 3.8 and have made our code publicly available (all libraries are listed there).
- Graphs are straightforward to reproduce.
- Collected user specific statistics are not well-documented or explained by the authors (e.g. focus).
- The dataset comes in three different csv files. There is no explanation about how to use these files or combine them for further computations. Since there is no user ID given, it is not clear how to get all data about a specific user.
- It is not clearly described how influence should be calculated - either by using the followers and likes csv files or the users data average values. Furthermore, the definition of influence does not allow users to watch videos multiple times. This usually happens, but the authors do not take this into account.
- No details are provided on the reduced feature elimination algorithm (not even which features were found to be significant and using what metrics). The default scikit-learn recursive feature elimination was thus used for the reproduction study.
- No details are provided on parameters used for building the baseline models, neither for the "minimal" nor for the "full" Ridge and Random Forest models. The default scikit-learn models were thus used.
- The r-squared and Spearman correlation coefficient are used as performance metrics and 5-fold cross-validation was performed as stated in the paper.
- In the paper it was stated that a K-means clustering was performed in order to build a multi-regression model for the subsets. Due to lack of any details we could not come up with a reasonable implementation that would logically separate the data into clusters. In fact, the data for each of the graphs looks like it belongs to one single cluster and it was thus concluded that this step would not produce viable results. Still, an attempt was made where the default scikit-learn K-Means clustering was applied to the data for $k = 2, 3, 4$ and 5 clusters. This produced extremely imbalanced clusters with as few as 1 instance in a given class (e.g. for $k=5$).
- The authors seem to agree that "Multi-Regression was not a useful approach" and the explanation above may be the reason.
- The usage of the PageRank algorithm in the paper for creation of the r_s score was not further explained nor was

the result of 0.673 listed in the results table. This gives the impression that the paper was finished in a rush.

- Baseline model results are comparable to those in the paper.
- Regression model results are somewhat comparable to those in the paper when using the R^2 performance metric, but were better when using the r_s performance metric.

Figure 2: (a) Views Histogram (Paper)

Figure 3: (a) Views Histogram (Reproduction)

Figure 4: (b) Views per Followers (Paper)

Figure 5: (b) Views per Followers (Reproduction)

Figure 6: (c) Views per Likes (Paper)

Figure 7: (c) Views per Likes (Reproduction)

4 RESULTS

Dataset Size

First, as discussed previously, the paper states that the data set contains a total of 940439 posts by 115044 Instagrammers. The data set downloaded showed a total of 1422894 posts by 114781 Instagrammers.

Graphs

A graphical comparison of figures from the paper and our reproduced ones is shown in Figures 2-7.

Figures 2 and 3 look very similar and may differ only by number of bins, which is unknown. However, the cyan-colored line represents the mean of the log-normal distribution, which was evaluated to be 745 whereas the paper states a mean of 748. Figures 4 and 5, as well as 6 and 7 seem to be identical.

K-means Clustering and Multi-regression modeling

The authors stated that a K-Means clustering was performed on the data as a means of separating the subsets, for the purpose of building a regression model on each subset (called the "Multiple-Regression model"). There again were no details on the input parameters for the

clustering algorithm were given. The authors argued in the paper that this was done as "not all influencers should be handled in the same manner and celebrities statistics would show vast differences than those of micro-influencers". Thus, a minimum cluster number was taken to be 2 and a K-Means clustering was applied to the data for $k=2, 3, 4$ and 5. As a result, the size of the smaller cluster for $k=2$ was 8 data points. For increasing k , the size of the smallest cluster would decrease even further. This has as a consequence the effect during the modeling stage where it was extremely hard to train and test a model. Especially stratified train-test splitting would not be feasible. Only clusters with $k=2$ or $k=3$ have enough data in the smallest cluster to perform a 5-fold cross-validation. Since the goal of the clustering is to use regression on celebrities separately, the first plot ($k=2$) seems to make the most sense from a purely technical point of view. See Figure 8 for two graphs showing clusters as calculated by the $k=2$ K-Means algorithm.

Figure 8: K-means clustering for $k=2$. Note that the smaller group contains 8 datapoints. Other graphs of clusters $k=3, 4$ and 5 are shown in the accompanying Jupyter notebook.

The results of this multi-regression are listed in Table 1 below. It is important to note here that our findings are in accordance to the paper where it was stated that amongst the models, "Multi-Regression was not a useful approach".

Baseline Modeling, Ridge Regression and Random Forest

Two natural baselines for measuring the influence based on audience size (followers) and engagement level (number of likes) were reproduced using scikit-learn's linear regression library. The R^2 and r_s performance metrics are listed in Table 1. It was attempted to calculate the baselines of the two clusters, but the algorithm failed as there is too little data for conducting cross-validation. From this point we thus only used the data from the large cluster when reporting the "clustered" results (as the authors still reported data for clustered and unclustered attempts).

Next, it was attempted to reproduce the Random Forest and Ridge Regression models. Yet again, without any parameters given, we chose a default path by applying scikit-learn's out-of-the-box models. The reproduced results differed from the paper - some significantly more than others and generally, the R^2 scores much more so than the r_s . In addition to the full models, a feature elimination was performed to obtain reduced models but it was not stated which feature reduction algorithm was used. For the reproduction,

Table 1: Performance scores from all models: comparison of paper and reproduction results

		Regression		Multi-Regression	
		R^2	r_s	R^2	r_s
full Ridge Regression	paper reproduced	0.725 0.677 (0.158)	0.848 0.816 (0.009)	0.727 0.584 (0.213)	0.821 0.823 (0.014)
full Random Forest	paper reproduced	0.626 0.626 (0.136)	0.869 0.869 (0.002)	0.621 0.702 (0.117)	0.861 0.868 (0.002)
min Ridge Regression	paper reproduced	0.723 0.671 (0.129)	0.818 0.838 (0.009)	0.727 0.600 (0.193)	0.818 0.837 (0.006)
min Random Forest	paper reproduced	0.616 0.611 (0.117)	0.864 0.864 (0.008)	0.611 0.711 (0.107)	0.859 0.868 (0.003)
Followers Baseline	paper reproduced	0.211 0.260 (0.241)	0.757 0.753 (0.003)	0.204 0.283 (0.084)	0.725 0.753 (0.003)
Likes Baseline	paper reproduced	0.666 0.683 (0.109)	0.859 0.845 (0.002)	0.654 0.625 (0.160)	0.853 0.845 (0.002)

it was decided to go with scikit-learns Recursive Feature Elimination. As an attempt at handling the influence of the random state we used several different random states for cross-validation and averaged the result. Results for Ridge Regression are an average of 100 random states and results from Random Forest are an average of 5 random states due to time constraints. The results for all models are summarized in Table 1. The results show that we obtained comparable results for the full models and results within 1 standard deviation of the reduced models.

PageRank Extension

It was briefly stated in the paper that for completeness purposes another model was made: a so-called "PageRank extension suggested by Egger". For this, the authors crawled Instagram, creating a commentators graph around their test users. Still, later on they noted that "due to resource and time constraints the PageRank algorithm was run on a subset of 10% of the users, resulting in an r_s score of 0.673, which was only better than the baseline (in the paper), making it a low-performing model. The authors attributed this to the "flow of information" on Instagram, without giving further evidence.

As this was outside of the scope of this paper, and as a reproduction attempt would require an exact copy of: 1. the exact users selected for the PageRank of which only 10% of the users posts were included and how these were filtered; 2. the exact time period of the crawling; it was concluded that such a study failed the necessary details and parameters for a reproduction and was not even remotely attempted.

Regression Results

In Table 1 we summarize and compare the results from the 24 reproduced models. One can find the standard deviations of the reproduced results in brackets. As briefly mentioned before, the R^2 scores are worse than the r_s scores. This may be due to the fact that Spearman's rank correlation coefficient measures the strength and direction of association between two ranked variables, while the R^2 score is a numerical figure for the amount of the variation between the model and the data points. As there is a logarithmic

trend in the strength and direction of the output variable, it can be postulated that Spearman's rank correlation coefficient is a better measure for the models.

5 CONCLUSION

This paper attempted to tackle the problem on how to identify and rank influential users of Instagram, an online social network, by using regression models from user statistics in order to predict influence per user. It was a cumbersome paper to reproduce, especially because there was little to no information on any data preprocessing or model implementation details. Even though the dataset was publicly available, it was not clearly described how it was processed to obtain the results. The figures could be reproduced nearly identically and their added features were well described. After this however, close to no details were given on how the dataset was handled. One problem that could not be solved even after considering several approaches was the reproduction of the univariate outlier removal. The computation of the baselines, regression models and the use of the recursive feature elimination worked to a certain extent, as we tried to find our own approach by guessing/using default settings of named algorithms. Furthermore, significance tests for each of the models were conducted using the t-test metric to compare the reproduced results with those reported in the paper. A number of tests showed that the null hypothesis could be rejected and that the reproduced results are not in agreement with those from the paper (for $N=5$).

We conclude that the discrepancies in the results can only be attributed to the failing details for the modeling part: preprocessing, environment, transformations of the data, parameters, clustering details, etc.

Finally, we arrive to one same conclusion as the authors of the paper, that "amongst our suggested models, Multi-Regression was not a useful approach" but differ in the part where they conclude that Ridge Regression was *significantly* better than Random Forest.

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